

UNIVERSITY BASKETBALL LEAGUE MANAGEMENT MODEL FOR SUSTAINABLE IN HUNAN PROVINCE, CHINA

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Abstract

For many years, Hunan Province has actively responded to the national call and organized University Basketball League. However, some shortcomings have gradually been exposed in the league management process. Therefore, I am conducting research in this area. The objective of this research were to :1) To study the current situation and affecting factors of university basketball league management for sustainable in Hunan province, China.2) To analyze factors positive effect university basketball league management for sustainable in Hunan province, China.3)To examine and evaluate university basketball league management for sustainable in Hunan province, China. This research employed a mixed research methodology combining a quantitative and qualitative research methods. Step 1: Through qualitative research, analyze and understand the current situation and influencing factors of sustainable development management in Hunan University Basketball League, with a total of 15 participants. Step 2: Through quantitative research, a survey questionnaire was distributed to collect data, and structural equation modeling (SEM) was used for analysis, with a total of 450 participants. Step 3: Through a combination of quantitative and qualitative research, 9 experts conducted focus group discussions and scoring. The research results indicate that: 1) There are several key aspects of the current situation of university basketball league management for sustainable in Hunan province, China: 1. Management level 2. Event quality 3. Human resource development 4. Funding and social activities 5. Innovation and improvement direction. These current situations reflect the actual situation of the management mode of the Hunan University Basketball League. By comprehensively analyzing these factors, the management level of the Hunan Province University Basketball League can be further improved. 2) Human resources, marketing management, guarantee system, and sports event management have a significant positive impact on the sustainable development management mode of Hunan Province's university basketball league. 3) Experts evaluate the feasibility, appropriateness, usefulness, and accuracy of the University basketball league management model for sustainable in Hunan province, China high level and their opinions remain consistent. This study helps to understand the basic situation and influencing factors of the University basketball league management model for sustainable in Hunan province, China and promote the continuous improvement and optimization of the university basketball league, and provide reference for relevant departments to formulate more effective strategies and methods.

Keywords: University Basketball League, Human Resources, Marketing Management, Guarantee system, Sports Event Management.

1. INTRODUCTION

Hunan Province has actively responded to the call for college student competitions for many years, but in the process of league management, many professional problems have gradually emerged. There are also many contradictions and problems that need to be solved in its development process, all due to inadequate management. Proper management is the foundation of development. The management of university sports events is an important means to ensure the smooth development of events, an effective way to improve the popularity of basketball in Hunan Province's universities, an important measure to promote the transformation of national sports, and also one of the means to promote personal development and social benefits. These suggestions aim to strengthen the management of the Hunan University Basketball League for reference by relevant stakeholders. This approach has promoted the continuous improvement and optimization of regional basketball competitions, and promoted the comprehensive development of basketball in Hunan Province.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 The relationship between the university basketball league management model for sustainable in Hunan province and Human resources factors

The human resources refers to the abilities and talents that can be utilized by the organization's personnel. These personnel can make contributions to achieve the organization's model, plans and goals (Li, 2022). The Human resource refers to the workforce of professional sportspersons who have received professional education and training in sports within the sports system, or who have received professional training in sports and are able to contribute to the development of sports, which involves the sports industry, school sports, and sports competitions (Ling, 2021).

2.2 The relationship between the university basketball league management model for sustainable in Hunan province and Marketing management factors

The marketing management refers to advertising, event sponsorship, personnel promotion, etc., examine products, industries, and consumers from a strategic perspective, and then formulate suitable integration model for the company Marketing (Zhang, 2023). The marketing management refers to the process of business activities aimed at meeting consumer needs and achieving corporate goals in a changing market environment, including market research, target market selection, product development, product pricing, A series of market-related business operations (Li, 2018).

2.3 The relationship between the university basketball league management model for sustainable in Hunan province and Guarantee system factors

The guarantee system refers to is viewed from the perspective of the policy guarantee, the government's emphasis on the city's characteristic sports culture, the internationalization of the event and the localization of the event, the construction of a diversified collaborative network, and the enrichment of the supply of sports facilities in order to improve the event guarantee

system (Wang, 2023). The guarantee system refers to the three levels of the government, school and society, the institutional setup, hardware resource allocation, teacher team construction, tournament system, publicity and promotion, and other aspects of the guarantee system such as strengthening the policy guarantee, providing financial guarantee, establishing a service platform, and improving the incentive mechanism (Zhang, 2022).

2.4 The relationship between the university basketball league management model for sustainable in Hunan province and Sports event management factors

The sports events management refers to the process of planning, organizing, reconciling and disposing of the resources related to the event by the event's organizer and responsible manager under the condition of limited resources, as well as complexity. The management process can be divided into the pre-event preparation phase, the event operation phase, and the post-event wrap-up phase (Liu, 2019). The sports events management refers to process of planning, organizing and coordinating the activities of the various stages of the event in order to effectively achieve the goals of the event, with the content of the event competition mainly based on the competition items, and the organization and management of the event (Kou, 2016).

2.5 Research Framework

This study uses Human resources factors, Marketing management factors, Guarantee system factors, Sports event management, and the university basketball league management model for sustainable in Hunan province, China the dependent variable. Based on the literature review and research objectives, a model of the university basketball league management model for sustainable in Hunan province a was constructed. Figure shows a diagram of this model.

Figure 1: Conceptual model

The conceptual model provides the basic hypothesized relationship between Human resources factors, Marketing management factors, Guarantee system factors, Sports event management and the management model of university basketball league in Hunan province. Assume the following:

- H1: Human resources factor affect management model of university basketball league in Hunan province.
- H2: Marketing management factor affect the management model of university basketball league in Hunan province.
- H3: Guarantee system factor affect the management model of university basketball league in Hunan province.
- H4: Sports event management factor affect the management model of university basketball league in Hunan province.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The first step is to collect data through in-depth interviews and analyze the current situation and influencing factors of the university basketball league management model for sustainable in Hunan province. The second step is to collect data using the China Online Questionnaire Platform, process and analyze the data using SPSS and Smart PLS 4.0 software, and construct the university basketball league management model for sustainable in Hunan province, China. The third step is examine and evaluate university basketball league management model for sustainable in Hunan province, China. By focus group discussions through content analysis and quantitative research, evaluate the assess feasibility, appropriateness, usefulness and accuracy university basketball league management model for sustainable in Hunan province, China.

The sample data for this study comes from within Hunan province. The sample is personnel related to the university basketball league management model for sustainable in Hunan province.,China.It is generally recommended that the sample size should be at least 20 times(Lindeman et al.,1980),dimension $17 \times 20 = 340$.To ensure the comprehensiveness of the research, the actual distribution of questionnaires should be greater than 340(Lindeman et al.,1980).Were selected for questionnaire survey and the data was collected by simple random sampling questionnaire total 450 people.

4. RESULTS

4.1 Qualitative analysis

4.1.1 Summary of the current situation

Experts have a relatively positive evaluation of the Hunan Provincial College Basketball League, believing that it has achieved certain results in competition organization and management. That the sustained support and funding from the Hunan Provincial Government for the Hunan Provincial College Basketball League reflects the government's emphasis and

commitment to the development of campus sports. The government has provided a solid foundation and guarantee for the smooth hosting of campus basketball events through various means such as funding, providing activity venues, and promoting publicity. The capital investment is mainly used for event organization, facility improvement, bonus setting, referee fees, etc., effectively improving the level and quality of competitions, and promoting the popularization and development of campus basketball culture. In terms of policy formulation and resource guarantee. The Ministry of Education should establish a comprehensive recruitment system for college athletes that is suitable for the national conditions, prevent outstanding basketball talents from being buried, introduce policies and employment security mechanisms that are more conducive to the employment of athletes, and increase employment opportunities for graduated basketball players. At the same time, the legal department should also strengthen the promulgation and improvement of laws and regulations related to the league, ensuring the legitimate rights and stable operation of the league.

In summary, the management mode of Hunan Provincial College Basketball League requires comprehensive measures to be taken from the aspects of event organization, marketing promotion, talent team construction, and event guarantee. By establishing a scientific and reasonable competition organization system, formulating effective marketing strategies, strengthening the cultivation and development of talent teams, optimizing the competition guarantee system, the quality and level of the league can be further improved, and sustainable development and long-term goals can be achieved.

4.1.2 Influencing factors

Human resources: Human resources are one of the important factors affecting the basketball league management model. The quality and quantity of the management team and staff directly affect the organizational efficiency and quality of the event.

Marketing management: The impact of marketing management on the Hunan College Basketball League cannot be ignored. Effective marketing strategies can enhance the visibility and appeal of the event, attract more spectators and sponsors to participate, and increase the event's revenue and resource investment.

Guarantee system: The guarantee system is the basic guarantee to ensure the smooth progress of the basketball league. Including safeguard measures in terms of event venue facilities, security, medical aid, etc. **Sports event management:** Sports event management refers to the comprehensive management of event organization, planning, execution and evaluation. Excellent sports event management can ensure the fairness, justice and professionalism of the event and improve the quality and level of the event.

Experts emphasized the importance of the four key factors of human resources, marketing management, security system and sports event management to the basketball league management model. The views of these experts emphasize the importance of all aspects of the basketball league management model, from talent training to event promotion, from safety and security to standardized management, which are all key factors to ensure the successful operation of the basketball league. By comprehensively utilizing these factors, the management

level of the Hunan College Basketball League can be further improved and the vigorous development of campus basketball can be promoted.

4.2 Quantitative analysis

4.2.1 Variable description and Trust level analysis

Descriptive statistics are conducted on the group names in the scale section, in order to determine the basic level of group names in the scale and the distribution of data presentation. The vast majority of indicator variable data exhibit a normal distribution. The Cronbach's Alpha coefficients of the main constructs and dimensions involved in this study are all greater than 0.7, meeting the corresponding judgment criteria, so the reliability of the sample scale is high.

4.2.2 Testing the reliability of the questionnaire

Table 1: second-order construct reliability test results table

Second-order construct	Number of measurement items	Cronbach's alpha(n=30)
Human resources	20	0.707
Marketing management	20	0.749
Guarantee system	15	0.711
Sports events management	15	0.804
University basketball league management model for sustainable in Hunan province, China	15	0.763

The Cronbach's alpha coefficient of each part is greater than 0.7, indicating that the questionnaire used in this study has good reliability.

4.2.3 Correlation analysis

Perform correlation analysis on variables in Human resources, Marketing management, Guarantee system, Sports event management, University basketball leadership management model for sustainable in Hunan province, etc.

Table 2: Correlation analysis between variables

Variable	A1	A2	A3	A4	A5	M1	CT5
A1	1							
A2	.640**	1						
A3	.644**	.621**	1					
A4	.769**	.690**	.654**	1				
A5	.682**	.599**	.622**	.666**	1			
M1	.438**	.411**	.388**	.400**	.394**	1		
.....	
CT5	.349**	.311**	.332**	.329**	.344**	.329**	1

From the data in the table, it can be seen that the Pearson correlation coefficient between most variables is greater than 0, and there is a significant positive correlation. It can be concluded that there is a significant correlation between each variable.

4.2.4 Structural equation model

This study used SmartPLS4 to establish a path model and imported the collected 450 sample data into it.

Figure 2: research path model diagram

4.2.5 Internal CR, AVE and Cronbach's Alpha

Table 3: Measure CR, AVE and Cronbach's Alpha values for variables in the model

Dimension	Cronbach's Alpha	Rho_A	Composite reliability	Average Extracted Variance (AVE)
Guarantee system	0.942	0.942	0.949	0.552
Human resources	0.948	0.948	0.953	0.504
Marketing management	0.884	0.885	0.920	0.525
Sports event management	0.931	0.931	0.939	0.509
university basketball league management model for sustainable in Hunan province, China	0.935	0.936	0.943	0.525

It can be seen that the combined reliability values of all variables are greater than 0.70, and Cronbach's Alpha values are also greater than 0.70. AVE values of each variable in this study are all above 0.50. Therefore, the variables in this study have internal consistency reliability. Variables in this study have convergent validity.

4.2.6 Evaluation of the Structural Model

4.2.6.1 Coefficient of determination)R²(

The R-squared explanatory power of endogenous latent variables is generally greater than 0.67, indicating a strong explanatory power, between 0.33-0.67 indicating moderate explanatory power, between 0.19-0.33 indicating a small explanatory power, and below 0.19 indicating almost no explanatory power.

Table 4 Fit R² of the model

Dimension	R ²	R ² adjusted	Result	Dimension	R ²	R ² adjusted	Result
A	0.733	0.732	High	MP	0.779	0.778	High
C	0.729	0.728	High	PD	0.746	0.746	High
CE	0.797	0.797	High	PE	0.770	0.769	High
CR	0.782	0.781	High	R	0.736	0.736	High
CT	0.755	0.755	High	SG	0.775	0.775	High
ES	0.717	0.716	High	SI	0.781	0.781	High
FG	0.811	0.811	High	SP	0.730	0.730	High
GM	0.771	0.770	High	TD	0.780	0.780	High
M	0.690	0.689	High				High
university basketball league management model for sustainable in Hunan province, China				0.572	0.568		Moderate

From Table 4, it can be seen that the R2 values of the endogenous latent variables in the path model of this study are mostly greater than 0.67. Only the university basketball leadership model for sustainable in Hunan province has an R2 value of 0.574. The explanatory power of the variables is moderate, indicating that the model has a good ability to explain latent variables.

4.2.6.2 Path coefficient size and Effect size (f²)

This study evaluated using PLS, the size of the path coefficient can provide information about the strength of the relationship between variables.

Table 5: Statistical Table of Path Coefficient Size

	Path coefficients	f ²	Result
Human resources->University basketball league management model for sustainable in Hunan province, China	0.335	0.117	Weak
Marketing management-> University basketball league management model for sustainable in Hunan province, China	0.230	0.187	Moderate
Guarantee system -> University basketball league management model for sustainable in Hunan province, China	0.260	0.086	Weak
Sports event management-> University basketball league management model for sustainable in Hunan province, China	0.183	0.058	Weak

From the table, it can be seen that the impact of each path is positive. The impact of Human resource, Guarantee system, and Sports event management on the University basketball leadership management model for sustainable in Hunan province, China is relatively small. The impact of marketing management is moderate.

4.2.6.3 Predictive relevance Q²

In the structural model, Q² represents the predicted correlation of the variable, and the larger the value, the stronger the predicted correlation.

Table 6: Predicted correlation scores

	SSO	Residual Sum of Squares (SSE)	Q ² (=1-SSE/SSO)	Result
university basketball league management model for sustainable in Hunan province, China	1350	650.563	0.518	High

The calculation results show that the Q-squared statistical correlation affecting the university basketball league management model for sustainable in Hunan province, China is 0.518, indicating that the selected Human resources, Marketing management, Guarantee system, and Sports event management have a high predictive effect on the variable measuring tools that affect the university basketball league management model for sustainable in Hunan province, China.

4.2.6.4 Path coefficient significance

The structural equation model mainly uses non parametric Bootstrapping programs to detect the significance of coefficients.

Table 7: Significant Test Results of Path Coefficients in Structural Equation Model

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	Significant t level	P values	Outcome
Human resources	0.268	0.268	0.037	7.324	***	0.000	Supported
Marketing management	0.312	0.310	0.040	7.779	***	0.000	Supported
Guarantee system	0.218	0.218	0.039	5.546	***	0.000	Supported
Sports event management	0.189	0.188	0.038	4.964	***	0.000	Supported

Note: NS=not significant, Not significant *p<0.10, **p<0.05, ***p<0.01

(1) Due to a t-value of 7.324, which is greater than 3.29, and a P-value of 0.000, Human resources have a significant impact on University basketball league management model for sustainable in Hunan province, with an estimated value of 0.268. (2) Due to a t-value of 7.779, which is greater than 3.29, and a P-value of 0.000, Marketing management factors have a significant impact on the University basketball league management model for sustainable in

Hunan province, with an estimated value of 0.312.(3) Due to a t-value of 5.546, greater than 3.29, and a P-value of 0.000, Guarantee system factors have a significant impact on the University basketball league management model for sustainable in Hunan province,with an estimated value of 0.218.(4) Due to a t-value of 4.964, greater than 3.29, and a P-value of 0.000, the Sports event management factors have a significant impact on the University basketball league management model for sustainable in Hunan province,with an estimated value of 0.189.All hypotheses are supported.

4.3 Evaluation model

4.3.1 Quantitative analysis

This study selected 9 experts with professional knowledge in the field of sustainable management of Hunan University Basketball League to ensure the scientificity and rationality of the evaluation standards and indicator systems to maximize the objectivity and accuracy of the evaluation results. The research results show that, the mean values of these data are all above 3.8, indicating that experts hold a relatively high evaluation of these evaluation items, and the standard deviations are all around 1, indicating that the experts' ratings are consistent.

4.3.2 Qualitative analysis

4.3.2.1 Human resource management and the sustainability of Hunan University Basketball League management

Experts believe that the management of Hunan Province's university basketball league reflects a high degree of autonomy and decision-making power of managers. Managers can independently decide on activity rules, fund utilization, organizational structure, and development direction. In terms of athletes, the league provides sufficient training resources and career development opportunities for college students, and establishes a scientific and fair selection and training system to protect the rights and interests of athletes. The coaching team possesses professional skills and qualities, and the alliance has established a comprehensive coach management system and selection and training system, promoting the collaborative spirit and social responsibility of coaches. The referee team possesses professional referee skills and qualities. The alliance ensures the quality and collaborative spirit of the referee team through a scientific and fair selection and training system, and is committed to maintaining the fairness and standardization of the competition.

4.3.2.2 Marketing management and sustainability of Hunan college basketball league management

From the perspective of marketing management, it can be seen that the sustainability of Hunan University Basketball League has achieved certain results in sponsorship activities. A small number of sponsors provided sufficient support for the event, but there is still room for further expansion. The management team should focus on maintaining and managing sponsorship relationships, ensuring that sponsors receive reasonable returns, and promoting the expansion of sponsorship activities to a wider range of areas. In terms of media promotion, the coverage is extensive and timely, but there is still room for improvement.

It is recommended that the management team strengthen cooperation with the media, optimize promotional strategies, improve the depth and comprehensiveness of reporting, in order to enhance the visibility and attractiveness of the league. There is still room for improvement in social participation. The management team should actively carry out more social activities and projects, strengthen cooperation with social organizations, enhance the influence and awareness of basketball in society, and obtain more resources.

4.3.2.3 Guarantee system and the sustainability of Hunan University Basketball League management

The sustainability of the Hunan Provincial College Basketball League shows certain advantages and potential in terms of guarantee system. Funding guarantee is an important part of the guarantee system. The league management team needs to ensure the reasonable allocation and use of funds, actively explore sponsorship and support channels, and ensure the smooth progress and long-term development of the event. Government management is a key link in the security system.

The management team should work closely with government departments to jointly formulate and improve management policies and promote the standardized and professional development of league management. Institutional guarantee is an important guarantee for the guarantee system. The management team should focus on system construction, constantly improve operational processes and organizational structure, promote the sustainable development of the league and enhance overall competitiveness.

4.3.2.4 Sports event management and the sustainability of Hunan University Basketball League management

Firstly, in the competition preparation stage, the management team demonstrated efficient and professional management skills. They have fully prepared the necessary venues, equipment, and personnel for the competition, and have formulated detailed competition plans and arrangements. Secondly, during the execution phase of the competition, the management team emphasizes the fair and just implementation of the competition rules, and is committed to creating a good competition atmosphere.

Valuing the competitive spirit and fair competition of athletes, striving to improve the viewing experience and participation in competitions, and providing high-quality sports event experiences for the audience and participants. The management team actively coordinates resources from all parties involved in the execution of the competition to ensure the smooth progress of the competition. Finally, in the post-match evaluation stage, a comprehensive reflection and summary were conducted on the Hunan Provincial College Basketball League.

In summary, the Hunan University Basketball League has demonstrated good sustainability in human resources, marketing, security system, and sports event management. Providing high-quality sports experience for athletes and spectators lays the foundation for the development and sustained success of the league.

5. CONCLUSION, DISCUSSION AND SUGGESTION

5.1 Conclusion

The influencing factors of the management mode of Hunan University Basketball League in this study are divided into Human resources, Marketing management, Guarantee system, and Sports event management. Multiple statistical methods and models are used for empirical testing. The results confirm that the proposed model of influencing factors of the management mode of Hunan University Basketball League and its four components maintain a close relationship. Therefore, this study helps to use structural equation models in various ways to measure the development factors of the management mode of Hunan University Basketball League. Among the factors that affect the management mode of the Hunan Provincial University Basketball League, it is better to promote the development of the University Basketball League management model for sustainable in Hunan Province, China, and have a significant impact on the management mode of the Hunan Provincial University Basketball League, thereby enhancing the sustainable development of the basketball league. This discovery has certain reference value for the development of the Chinese University Basketball League, and can provide them with more effective strategies and methods to improve the development of the basketball league.

5.2 Discussion

5.2.1 The relationship between Human resources and University Basketball League Management model for Sustainable in Hunan province, china

This study aims to explore the relationship between Human resources factors and University Basketball League Management model for Sustainable in Hunan province, China. This research result confirms the view of H1 in this study and proves the positive impact of Human resources factors on the University Basketball League Management model for Sustainable in Hunan province, China. Chen (2017) found that high levels of athlete participation can enhance the competition level of the league and attract more spectators and sponsors to participate. In addition, research by Brown et al. (2019) shows that athletes technical and physical fitness levels will affect the leagues competition system design and schedule, which will have an important impact on the league model.

5.2.2 The relationship between Marketing management and University Basketball League Management model for Sustainable in Hunan province, china

This study aims to explore the relationship between Marketing management factors and the sustainable management model of Hunan University Basketball League. This research result confirms the view of H2 in this study and proves the positive impact of marketing management factors on the sustainable management model of the Hunan College Basketball League. In college basketball leagues, event sponsorship is one of the important factors to ensure the sustainability and development of the league. The support of sponsors can provide funds and resources for the league and help increase the popularity and influence of the league, thereby attracting more participants and viewers (Chen, 2017).

5.2.3 The relationship between Guarantee system and University Basketball League Management model for Sustainable in Hunan province, china

This study aims to explore the relationship between Guarantee system factors and the sustainable management model of the Hunan College Basketball League. This research result confirms the view of H3 in this study and proves the positive impact of Guarantee system factors on the sustainable management model of the Hunan College Basketball League. System guarantee has a comprehensive and far-reaching impact on the management model of college basketball leagues. By establishing a sound event management system, the management level and operational efficiency of the league can be improved, and a good competitive environment and experience can be provided for participants (Xiong, 2012).

5.2.4 The relationship between Sports event management and University Basketball League Management model for Sustainable in Hunan province, china

This study aims to explore the relationship between event management and the sustainable management model of the Hunan College Basketball League. This research result confirms the view of H4 in this study and proves the positive impact of event management factors on the sustainable management model of the Hunan College Basketball League. Post-game evaluation includes comprehensive analysis and evaluation of game results, operational effects, and participant feedback (Ming, 2019). The impact of competitive preparation on the management model of college basketball leagues is comprehensive and far-reaching. Through effective competitive preparation, the overall level and influence of the league can be improved, the competitiveness and cohesion of participating teams can be enhanced, and the league can be promoted in a healthier and sustainable direction (Zhong, 2023).

5.3 Discussion and Suggestion

This study combines the current situation of sustainable development of the management mode of Hunan University Basketball League, and analyzes the management model of the college basketball league in Hunan Province based on factors such as Human resources, Marketing management, Guarantee system, and Sports event management. On the impact of sustainable development, based on the relationship between these variables, an overall research framework suitable for the sustainable development management model of the Hunan College Basketball League was established and hypotheses were made. Finally, the future development direction of the sustainable development of the Hunan College Basketball League management model is prospected. Proposed to strengthen the promotion of the competition, provide more technical guidance and training resources, and help players comprehensively develop their skills; Establish a recruitment system for college athletes that is suitable for the national conditions, introduce policies and employment protection mechanisms that are more conducive to athlete employment, and ensure the legitimate rights and stable operation of the alliance, among many reasonable suggestions. Follow-up research can consider adding or replacing variables in the research model so that the model can fully reflect the factors that affect the sustainable development of the Hunan College Basketball League management model.

Reference

- 1) Zhang, M, Y. (2022). Research on the operation mode of university basketball league in China. *Arts and Sporting Goods and Technology*.(10),159-161.
- 2) Cui, Y. (2020) Master's thesis on the comparative study of athlete management models in the Chinese and American University Basketball League, Qufu Normal University.
- 3) Zhou, Q. H. (2021) Research on the Operation of AUBA University Basketball League (Master's Thesis, Jishou University).
- 4) Ji, H. P. (2019). Research on Basketball Competition Management for College Students in Henan Province (Master's Thesis, Henan University).
- 5) Lin, M. D.(2018). Research on the Operation and Management Model of the Three on Three Basketball League Finals for World University Students (Master's Thesis, Fujian Normal University).
- 6) Huang, Y. J. (2021) Master's thesis on the influencing factors and development paths of promoting small basketball in Jiangsu Province, China University of Mining and Technology.
- 7) Li, L. B. (2021) Doctoral Dissertation on the Impact and Prediction of Digital Transformation on Human Resource Demand of Agricultural Bank of China, Beijing Jiaotong University.
- 8) Sun, Y. Q.(2020) Master's thesis on the current situation and countermeasures of high-level men's basketball teams in Hunan Province's CUBA, Jishou University.
- 9) Tu, C. Q. (2021) Master's thesis on the current marketing situation and optimization strategies of Shanxi Guotou Professional Basketball Club, Central North University.
- 10) Xiang, L. (2020) Master's thesis on the influencing factors of the development of Shanghai Campus Volleyball League under the WSR framework, Shanghai Institute of Physical Education.
- 11) Zhang, Y. A. (2021) Master's thesis on the current situation and countermeasures of the development of the three player basketball league in Hunan Province, Jishou University.